

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

5.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on public health responses and impacts - update M35

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Executive Summary

The empirical research conducted in the COVINFORM project is centred around assessing COVID-19 impact, response, and lessons learned across diverse local contexts. The empirical research conducted in the context of WP5 specifically aims to explore COVID-19 impact, response and lessons learned from a public health perspective. The current deliverable (D5.8) mainly focuses on synthesizing data that is drawn from WP5 desktop and empirical research. The current deliverable is a synthesis of the analysis conducted in D5.7 (Public health responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment), which further drew upon previous deliverables and expert interviews.

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1 Introduction

The COVINFORM project examines how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project draws upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation. The project addresses the following top-level research questions, within the target countries and municipalities, across several work packages:

- **RQ1:** How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- **RQ2:** How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- **RQ3:** What were the lived experiences of the pandemic/crisis management within certain vulnerable groups across diverse local contexts?
- **RQ4:** Which barriers, unintended consequences, trade-offs, lessons learned and promising practices can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

Within this broader context, WP5 analyses COVID-19's impact and response from a public health perspective, with a specific focus on health inequality and vulnerability. The main overarching research questions that have been defined for WP5, are as follows:

- **WP5 RQ1:** How have COVID-19 public health responses been received, implemented and adapted across diverse local contexts and groups?
- **WP5 RQ2:** How have vulnerabilities and structural health inequalities been addressed and/or exacerbated by COVID-19 public health responses?
- **WP5 RQ3:** How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted health workers across diverse contexts and care settings?

The COVID-19 pandemic prompted a range of responses across different countries, reflecting their unique contexts, governance structures, and societal dynamics. The responses reveal successful strategies, lessons learned, and challenges and adaptations that emerged over time. Here, we compare and synthesize the COVID-19 public health responses in Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales, focusing on how these responses were received, implemented, and adapted across diverse local contexts and groups. Next, we will look at how the COVID-19 pandemic has laid bare vulnerabilities and structural health inequalities within various countries. In the face of this crisis, responses have ranged from targeted interventions to inadvertent exacerbation of existing disparities. This analysis examines how countries addressed and sometimes aggravated these challenges. Finally, we will explore how the COVID-19 pandemic has had profound effects on healthcare workers (HCWs) across diverse contexts and care settings. This deliverable will be a synthesis of the country reports in D5.7, however, it will also be drawing upon empirical research conducted throughout the project, as well as other deliverables.

2 How have COVID-19 public health responses been received, implemented and adapted across diverse local contexts and groups? Lessons learnt and promising practices across countries

2.1 Initial response and public reception

In most countries, including Austria and Greece, COVID-19 public health responses were initially well received by the majority of citizens, especially during the early stages of the pandemic. There was a high degree of solidarity amongst the public and significant portions of the population supported swift actions, such as business closures and curfews. In fact, in many cases, the delayed implementation of the lockdown created problems for vulnerable groups, and the proportion of those who would have liked to see stricter measures and rules exceeded those who would like to see them relaxed. In England, for example, the response was initially slow compared to other European countries, partly due to poor leadership, underfunding of the healthcare system and existing workforce problems. In Sweden, achieving herd immunity with a “flattening the curve” was first implemented as the main strategy, although the country later pivoted towards a more balanced approach. The virus was still not considered a mortal threat to people not belonging to high-risk groups (elderly, those with underlying illnesses). In both countries, this likely led to higher levels of transmission, deaths, and additional challenges faced by vulnerable groups such as the elderly. In Portugal, however, the quick implementation of a state of emergency, along with measures like lockdowns and travel restrictions, demonstrated the government's commitment to containing the virus.

Over time, however, in all countries, satisfaction with measures waned, and skepticism emerged regarding certain strategies like testing and contact tracing. Trust in public health institutions remained relatively steady, while political institutions faced declining trust, a trend observed in Austria and Spain. In Portugal, the government received praise for its swift response, but as the pandemic persisted, frustration and fatigue grew. Protests against COVID-19 measures occurred, reflecting some skepticism about the severity of the threat. Similarly, in Greece, the initial high acceptance and awareness of COVID-19 public health responses demonstrated the importance of effective communication and transparent information dissemination. However, the gradual trust decline highlights the need for consistent and clear communication throughout the pandemic. In Germany, public reactions to measures were monitored through the COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring project, revealing fluctuations in trust in health institutions and the federal government, as well as varying levels of compliance with measures like mask-wearing. Agreement with COVID-19 measures and readiness to protest against them also showed fluctuating patterns, with some expressing frustration over perceived excessiveness. The healthcare workers interviewed expressed diverse viewpoints, commenting on aspects of pandemic governance, risk communication, and lack of tolerance for differing opinions. While their attitudes were more about questioning and critically accepting measures rather than fully rejecting them, the broader population's readiness to protest remained relatively low.

Promising practices include ongoing engagement with diverse local contexts and groups to address concerns and ensure compliance with measures and strategies to counteract the spread of misinformation. A valuable lesson learned was the importance of effective communication and

engagement with the public. While initial measures received widespread support, growing frustration and fatigue highlighted the need for sustained communication and transparency. Adapting communication strategies to address diverse local contexts and population segments could enhance compliance and reduce distrust.

2.2 Adaptation and flexibility

One challenge faced by many countries in adapting to the evolving situation was the lack of a national pandemic plan. Often the only preparedness, which countries had were, outdated influenza plans, which limited the response. Other structural factors prevented countries from adapting so easily to the pandemic. In Belgium, a complex government structure led to confusion and inefficiencies in crisis management, with a division of responsibilities at the federal, regional, and local levels. The creation of a caretaker government also added to these issues. Similarly, Spain's decentralized structure required effective coordination between the central government and autonomous communities. Co-governance mechanisms were developed to enhance collaboration, albeit amidst political tensions. This unified decision-making approach ensured equal participation of various levels of management, leading to rapid decisions based on technical-scientific evidence. This collaborative structure increased accountability and facilitated swift responses. Future responses can benefit from strengthened multilevel structures and coordination mechanisms. Wales adopted a collaborative approach between the Welsh Government, Public Health Wales and other institutions, gradually asserting its independence from the UK-wide response. The implementation of measures in Wales involved a learning curve, with cross-organizational agreement recognized as more important than the speed of announcements. A lesson learned was the need for improved coordination and communication between different levels of decision-makers.

Italy decentralized National Health Plan (SSN) demonstrated the importance of functional cooperation between different hospital facilities during the pandemic. The creation of a network for coordinated management played a crucial role in effectively responding to the crisis. However, the varying responses across different regions highlighted the challenge of achieving consistent implementation. Promising practices include fostering collaboration between the central government and regions, enhancing data collection and monitoring capabilities, and ensuring that communication strategies are uniform and effective across the country. Furthermore, in Portugal, collaboration between the Directorate-General of Health and the National Civil Protection Authority enabled a coordinated national response. The National Contingency Plan for SARS-CoV-2 Infection guided the crisis management, including surveillance, testing, healthcare response, and communication initiatives. The government collaborated with the National Civil Protection Authority and established a task force for COVID-19 vaccination, which later proved successful. As vaccination became widely available, Portugal gradually lifted restrictions. Meanwhile in Austria, the vaccination strategy was generally perceived as not very successful, and there were mixed feelings about the implementation of the contact tracing system. However, testing was considered an overall success.

Effective collaboration between government levels and scientific communities, as seen in Spain and Italy, emerged as a promising practice. Close cooperation with European and international bodies further bolstered technical-scientific cooperation. Both Portugal and Italy emphasized the importance of adapting communication strategies and engaging with the public to address evolving concerns and maintain compliance. Sweden's strategy evolved from a controversial initial approach to a more balanced one, reflecting the importance of ongoing adaptation.

2.3 Conclusion

The COVID-19 public health responses varied significantly across the countries, shaping a diverse landscape of successes, challenges, and adaptive strategies. Effective and sustained communication, transparent governance, engagement with local contexts and collaboration between government levels emerged as pivotal factors. Adapting responses to accommodate diverse local contexts and vulnerable populations remains a continuous challenge.

3 How have vulnerabilities and structural health inequalities been addressed and/or exacerbated by COVID-19 public health responses? Lessons learnt and promising practices across countries

3.1 Introduction

The response to the COVID-19 pandemic on a global scale has been characterized by shifting priorities in tackling vulnerability. This section will first delve into the process of identifying vulnerability, along with the intricate challenges related to data protection. Subsequently, it will delve into the strategies employed to shield vulnerable groups, highlighting their limitations. Finally, the unintended consequences of these measures are going to be examined; shedding light on how the pandemic and its aftermath exacerbated existing structural inequalities and vulnerabilities.

3.2 Identifying vulnerable groups

In many countries including Belgium, the focus was initially on physical vulnerability, with less attention to social vulnerability. However as the pandemic progressed, more attention was given to social vulnerability, and measures were introduced to address the needs of vulnerable populations. Similarly, the German federal government initially defined "at-risk groups" based on factors that increased the severity of COVID-19 progression, including age, pre-existing medical conditions, and smoking. As the pandemic progressed, definitions expanded to include those at risk of exposure, such as healthcare and front-line workers. Measures were taken to protect these vulnerable groups, including prioritized access to tests, protective equipment, care facilities, and vaccines. In Germany, *The Evaluation* comments on the National Pandemic Plan for insufficient consideration of complex social and cultural factors such as migration status/background, recommending that social determinants should be explicitly included in pandemic plans in the future, documents and evaluations often overlooked the interconnectedness of health and non-health vulnerabilities. The experience of HCWs and the impact on various vulnerable groups underscore the need for a more holistic approach to addressing structural health inequalities.

In Austria and Greece, vulnerable populations such as the elderly, chronically ill, pregnant women, and migrants were identified as at-risk groups. Vulnerabilities were identified based on clinical and social criteria. Vulnerable groups included those with pre-existing health conditions, the elderly, ethnic communities, and individuals with disabilities. Public health strategies aimed to protect these vulnerable groups by adjusting pandemic measures and vaccination efforts. Lessons learned include the recognition of changing dimensions of vulnerability during the pandemic and the importance of

addressing diverse social determinants of health, such as social deprivation and mental health. Spain pursued a holistic approach that encompassed refugees, migrants, and domestic violence victims. Sweden identified early the elderly, people with underlying health conditions, and migrants as vulnerable groups, yet they still faced disparities in resources and protective measures and the slow implementation of the lockdown created problems for them. Portugal's effective response included measures to support vulnerable groups and expand healthcare services, highlighting the importance of equitable access.

3.3 Data collection and health protection

During the pandemic, the tension between data protection and health protection underscored the complexity of addressing vulnerabilities. Austria encountered issues with disaggregated data collection due to strict data protection laws, hindering the identification of risk and vulnerability indices. Health data is identified as a special form of data and is therefore not easily accessible for public health institutions. Because of this reason, it was not simple to identify health vulnerabilities. One respondent from Belgium stressed the need for operational research to inform and guide decision-making. He suggested that data should be made available immediately to researchers, who can then use it to steer decision-making. In Belgium, pressure mounted for the release of detailed data, necessitating transparent communication. Austria and Greece also highlighted the need to address data protection concerns and misinformation to maintain public trust. The population's perception of measures evolved, giving rise to skepticism, particularly concerning surveillance-oriented strategies like testing and contact tracing. In the case of Spain, however, achieving effective vulnerability mitigation required consistent and comparable data collection along with standardized testing criteria. Enhanced data sharing and analysis have the potential to bolster response strategies, catering to diverse population segments. Thus, the predicament of striking a balance between data protection and public health came to the forefront, raising concerns about safeguarding both data and health.

3.4 Targeted measures and unintended consequences

During the pandemic, measures aimed at safeguarding vulnerable groups yielded mixed results and unintended outcomes. Targeted measures were initially focused on physical vulnerability, and reducing loss of life. Certain groups, such as elderly individuals with pre-existing health conditions, were considered more vulnerable to severe outcomes from COVID-19, leading to efforts for their protection, for example limiting visits to care facilities. In Portugal, telemedicine services were expanded for chronic health conditions, and specialized care homes were established. However, delays in locking down and a lack of pandemic preparedness meant that in most countries, these groups were not sufficiently protected. For example, in Italy, Sweden, Belgium, England and other countries, problems in care homes and hospitals partly resulted from a lack of PPE, highlighting the need for improved infrastructure and support for elderly and vulnerable individuals. Portugal demonstrated promising practices by establishing specific care homes for COVID-19 patients and expanding telemedicine services for individuals with chronic conditions. These measures aimed to safeguard vulnerable groups and ensure continued access to care. However, the COVID-19 pandemic also exposed vulnerabilities in countries healthcare systems, which were often under-resourced and underfunded. This meant there were shortages of personal protective equipment, beds in intensive care units and medical personnel, further increasing the risk to patients and healthcare workers. In Austria, the medical system's strain affected both patients and healthcare workers, leading to issues

like burnout among medical staff. In Spain, limited testing and discrepancies in testing criteria hindered tracking asymptomatic cases.

Socio-economic vulnerabilities, including those related to class, gender and ethnic background, were exacerbated, as crowded living conditions and overrepresentation in essential professions increased exposure to the virus. Vulnerable populations, including the elderly, women, people with disabilities, and immigrants in irregular situations, faced increased risks. They faced challenges in complying with measures, experiencing extended quarantine periods, and losing income. In Portugal, vulnerable groups, such as low-income workers, immigrants, and refugees, also encountered obstacles accessing healthcare and support. Vulnerable populations, such as the elderly and marginalized communities, faced heightened risks due to disparities in healthcare access. Disruptions in non-COVID healthcare services worsened structural inequalities, leaving some with limited access to necessary medical care. In many countries, there were delays in cancer treatment, disruptions in prevention and early diagnosis, and exacerbation of mental health problems in certain groups. In Austria, persons with physical disabilities, especially those who are blind or visually impaired, faced challenges due to reduced support services and discrimination. Lessons learned underscore the importance of tailoring support measures to address the specific needs of vulnerable groups, ensuring equitable access to healthcare and resources. The crisis also revealed the importance of addressing social determinants of health to mitigate inequalities. Promising practices include targeted interventions for vulnerable groups, ensuring access to adequate personal protective equipment, strengthening healthcare-associated infection control in institutions, and developing inclusive strategies for healthcare delivery. The response also highlighted the need for better coordination between different levels of government and healthcare providers to address these vulnerabilities.

The economic impact of the pandemic further heightened vulnerabilities. In Italy, the economic impact of the pandemic, particularly in industries like tourism and hospitality, worsened structural inequalities. In Belgium, policies were criticised for focusing on middle-class groups, who had access to a garden, and in general faced challenges in balancing uniform guidelines with localized needs, particularly for vulnerable populations. The pandemic exacerbated mental health issues and loneliness, particularly among isolated groups like young migrants and the clinically extremely vulnerable (CEV). Domestic abuse escalated during lockdowns, with barriers to accessing support and missed opportunities for intervention. The impact on children and their parents, especially during school closures, highlighted new forms of vulnerability. Sex workers, addicts, and the mentally ill were also disproportionately affected, with their vulnerabilities exacerbated. Digital solutions excluded those with limited digital skills or language barriers. Belgium's emphasis on involving local leaders to reach non-native speakers highlighted effective community engagement. Investing in robust social services and infrastructure is crucial for protecting vulnerable groups during crises, highlighting the importance of addressing social inequalities and mental health issues in crisis response strategies. Measures to ensure access to food, telecare, mental health support, and safe accommodations demonstrated positive impacts. Spain recognized the impact of socio-economic factors on vulnerability and implemented social services to support at-risk populations. These specialized measures include homeless care, home-based care, protection of children, and addressing gender-based violence. Greece's holistic approach with the inclusion of refugees and migrants in vaccination efforts demonstrated a commitment to equitable healthcare access. This highlighted the significance of addressing specific needs and tailoring support accordingly. Promising practices involve sustained

efforts to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities while fostering a society that is resilient and responsive to the needs of all citizens, particularly those at risk.

3.5 Conclusion

COVID-19 public health responses shed light on pre-existing vulnerabilities and health inequalities, showing varying degrees of success in addressing and mitigating these. The pandemic emphasized the need to address socio-economic inequalities comprehensively and ensure equitable access to healthcare and resources. Targeted interventions, inclusive policies, consistent data collection and recognition of socio-economic factors emerged as promising practices, alongside strengthened social services, and better coordination between government levels and healthcare providers. These lessons should inform future pandemic preparedness and response strategies to ensure equitable care for all segments of society.

4 RQ3: How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted health care workers across diverse contexts and care settings? Lessons learnt and promising practices across countries

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly affected healthcare workers (HCWs) worldwide, exposing them to a range of challenges and vulnerabilities across various care settings. This section will first explore how the pandemic exacerbated the vulnerabilities of medical and care workers across various European countries. Subsequently, we will explore the underlying structural factors contributing to these vulnerabilities, incorporating valuable lessons learned and promising practices that have emerged during the pandemic.

4.1 Vulnerabilities of healthcare workers

In all countries, the rapid adaptation of healthcare workers to challenging conditions and changing demands and protocols underscored their dedication and resilience, however in all countries, the initial lack of protective equipment contributed to increased vulnerability to COVID-19. In spring 2020, there was a shortage of personal protective equipment (PPE), including a slow distribution of facemasks. This created difficulties for health workers. The lack of PPEs negatively affected also care homes. The fear of infection also led to psychosomatic health issues among medical and care staff, including burnout, where seeking help was sometimes hindered by stigma. HCWs not only faced higher exposure risks but also experienced overwork, burnout, and psychological hardships. The inadequacy of economic and psychosocial support for HCWs became evident, when they often faced financial difficulties and longer working hours in Austria for example. In England, the underfunded NHS faced further strains during the pandemic, with workforce shortage and heightened demand in areas of high socioeconomic disadvantage. Healthcare workers faced issues with contact tracing, testing, and adherence to isolation guidance. Similarly, in Wales, the pandemic placed increased demands on the healthcare system, including staffing and resource limitations. Whilst healthcare workers were initially recognized as heroes, in Italy, this shifted to challenges and even blame as the pandemic progressed. In Sweden, mental stress on healthcare workers was exacerbated by negative media coverage and

threats on social media and in Austria, healthcare workers even witnessed violence in patient care. The pandemic also emphasized the undervaluing of the care sector within society, where vulnerabilities were highlighted among informal caregivers, and care workers, who often face poor working conditions and inadequate support. Shortages of personal protective equipment and high levels of staff turnover in elderly care contributed to increased workload and stress. There were also concerns among care workers about becoming infected and passing on the infection to their families.

4.2 Lessons learnt

In response, Austria established a Long-Term Care support fund and options for transnational mobility, although these measures were criticized for not fully addressing underlying flaws. The Belgian government invested in wages, working conditions, and personnel in response, but this was arguably not enough and the transformation of healthcare conditions still led to physical and psycho-emotional strain on workers. Addressing the inequity in remuneration and recognition of health and care workers is vital. COVID-19 highlighted how valuable this sector is, and providing decent pay and better working conditions should be the baseline, with health systems facing strained healthcare staffing and resources even prior to the pandemic. The pandemic highlighted shortcomings in supporting healthcare workers' mental health, revealing the need for comprehensive and tailored assistance programs and better support and screening programs for healthcare workers' psychological well-being. Ensuring comprehensive mental health support and resources is also crucial including mental health resources, training, and recognition of their contributions. Lessons learned include fostering an environment where professionals can openly address their challenges and seek assistance when needed. Greece highlighted that the lack of open communication about mental health issues underscores the need for dedicated support platforms for healthcare workers to discuss their experiences. The necessity for robust infrastructure and equipment in healthcare settings is also necessary to ensure the safety and well-being of medical personnel, for example through the provision of PPE and other measures. Issues of violence and discrimination could be addressed with the fostering of public appreciation and respect for their work.

4.3 Promising practices

Promising practices emerged through mutual support networks among HCWs, underscoring the importance of fostering a sense of community during crises. In Sweden, there was increased cohesion within teams and a greater understanding of each other's tasks. Rapid decision-making through collaboration and equal participation of healthcare professionals from various levels enabled efficient responses in Spain. Clear and consistent communication between decision-makers and healthcare workers was also vital. Lessons learned highlight the importance of providing timely and accurate information to healthcare professionals to ensure their well-being and effective response. It was also important to recognize different contexts and specialties within the healthcare sector because while some HCWs experienced increased workloads, others faced reduced consultations. Future responses should account for these variations to ensure adequate support for all healthcare professionals. Healthcare workers also experienced burdens related to unclear guidance, lack of leadership, and concerns over legal accountability. Local crisis management and operational research were emphasized as important for future preparedness, as well as improved accessibility of digital services, so they can better conduct teleconsultations. In Portugal and elsewhere, vaccination efforts positively

affected the working environment, reducing concerns and risks, protecting HCWs but also enhancing doctor-patient interactions by providing a sense of security.

4.4 Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has had profound effects on healthcare workers (HCWs) across diverse contexts and care settings. Across countries, HCWs encountered a range of challenges, including increased workloads, heightened exposure risks, shortages of personal protective equipment (PPE), and mental health strains. The structural underfunding and under-resourcing of health systems, with staff often underpaid and overworked, exacerbated the crisis faced during COVID-19. These cross-country insights underline the urgent need for comprehensive and adaptable support systems for HCWs, including mental health resources, comprehensive preparedness plans, clear communication, leadership support, and decent, equitable pay and recognition.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the responses to the research questions provide comprehensive insights into the multifaceted impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. They reveal the mixed implementation and reception of public health responses, the need to address vulnerabilities and structural health inequalities, and the challenges faced by healthcare workers.

Many countries initially received public health responses positively, with citizens showing solidarity and supporting measures such as lockdowns and curfews. However, as the pandemic progressed, satisfaction with these measures waned, leading to skepticism, especially in areas such as testing and contact tracing. Promising practices emerged from these experiences, emphasizing ongoing engagement with diverse local contexts and groups to address concerns and ensure compliance, as well as the importance of sustained communication and transparency in decision-making.

As the pandemic progressed, attention shifted from focusing on physical vulnerability towards social vulnerability, and measures were introduced to address the needs of vulnerable populations. The tension between data protection and health protection highlighted the challenges of collecting data to identify risk and vulnerability indices. Targeted measures for vulnerable groups, such as the elderly and those with pre-existing health conditions, yielded mixed results due to delays in implementing protective measures. Socio-economic vulnerabilities, including class, gender, and ethnic background, were exacerbated by the pandemic, with disparities in healthcare access and disrupted non-COVID healthcare services.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers (HCWs) was profound and varied across different countries and care settings. HCWs faced challenges related to the shortage of personal protective equipment (PPE), increased workloads, heightened exposure risks, and mental health strains. Despite their resilience and dedication, the inadequacy of support systems and resources, compounded by existing structural underfunding and staffing issues, intensified the crisis faced by HCWs. The lessons learned underscored the urgent need for comprehensive support systems, including mental health resources, preparedness plans, leadership support, equitable pay, and recognition. The pandemic also exposed vulnerabilities in the broader care sector, including informal caregivers and care workers who faced poor working conditions and inadequate support.

Although the pandemic revealed useful insights into specific promising practices and targeted lessons learnt, it highlighted that structural changes are needed to address socio-economic inequalities and vulnerabilities in society. These inequalities were already present prior to the pandemic, and have been further accentuated by its impact.